

Comparative study of processing methods for $(\text{NbTi})_{1-x}(\text{CrAl})_x$ RMPEAs: Microstructural and oxidation insights

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Refractory Multi-Principal Element Alloys (RMPEAs) are promising materials for high-temperature applications due to their remarkable properties, such as high thermal stability and excellent mechanical properties [1]. Synthesis via mechanical alloying followed by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) has demonstrate advantages over conventional melting methods [2]. This study investigates and compares the effects of different processing methods on the $(\text{NbTi})_{1-x}(\text{CrAl})_x$ ($x = 12.5$ and 25.0 at. %) RMPEAs. The alloys were produced via arc melting and via SPS at 1300°C for 60 min under 50 MPa [3]. The alloys were then characterized by SEM/EDS, XRD and subjected to oxidation tests in TGA at 1000°C for 20h in synthetic air. The XRD and SEM/EDS analysis indicated a single-phase body-centered cubic (BCC) solid solution microstructure with dendritic morphology in the as-cast samples. In contrast, SPS-sintered samples exhibited a BCC matrix with fine oxide precipitates. Furthermore, SPS processing led to more refined microstructure, enabling greater grain growth control compared to the as-cast alloys. Analysis of the oxidation kinetic parameters revealed that the $(\text{NbTi})_{75}(\text{CrAl})_{25}$ alloy exhibited a lower time constant than the $(\text{NbTi})_{87.5}(\text{CrAl})_{12.5}$ alloy in both processing methods, demonstrating the beneficial effect of the higher Cr and Al content on oxidation resistance. However, the SPS-sintered alloys exhibited a more pronounced transition to the parabolic regime. This behavior can be attributed to the microstructural characteristics of the processing route, including the presence of homogeneously distributed non-metallic particles and fine-grained microstructures. These factors promote the formation of more efficient diffusion barriers against oxygen ingress.

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